

SECTION OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ПРИНЦИПЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ КОРПОРАТИВНОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ АКЦИОНЕРНЫХ ОБЩЕСТВ

Акрамова Н.И.

Независимый исследователь Ташкентского государственного экономического университета

THEORETICAL PRINCIPLES OF FORMATION OF CORPORATE CULTURE OF JOINT STOCK COMPANIES

Akramova N.

Independent researcher of Tashkent State University of Economics

Аннотация

В статье раскрываются теоретические принципы формирования корпоративной культуры акционерных обществ. Выявлены этапы и технологии ее формирования. Как известно, культура предприятия определяет его своеобразие, уникальность. Следовательно, успешная адаптация человека к организации обуславливается не только выполнением должностных обязанностей и распоряжений руководства, но и встраиванием в корпоративную культуру путем деления общих ценностей и принятия существующих правил и норм поведения, и взаимодействия.

Abstract

The article reveals the theoretical principles of the formation of the corporate culture of joint-stock companies. The stages and technologies of its formation are revealed. As you know, the culture of the enterprise determines its originality, uniqueness. Consequently, the successful adaptation of a person to the organization is determined not only by the fulfillment of official duties and orders of the management, but also by embedding in the corporate culture by sharing common values and accepting the existing rules and norms of behavior and interaction.

Ключевые слова: корпоративная культура, признаки, принципы, подходы, технологии.

Keywords: corporate culture, features, principles, approaches, technologies.

INTRODUCTION.

The ever-growing interest in the global practice to the phenomenon of corporate culture, which is currently observed, is due to a number of reasons. Even despite the fact that, due to its interdisciplinary position, the term "corporate culture" does not have one generally accepted definition, researchers, scientists, managers, etc. recognize its significant practical significance in the functioning of any organization, firm, enterprise. This statement is a completely logical conclusion, since the foundation of every enterprise is people. It is the personnel that are the "core" of the organization, its driving force, and, therefore, the future success or failure of the organization directly depends on the amount of effort applied by the staff. The situation in the world markets today dictates the style of managing their companies to the heads of the largest corporations. Since today fierce rivalry is no longer so much in the context of the features and properties of manufactured goods and services, as well as marketing, but in the context of the level of corporate culture and personnel reserves. Progress and successful functioning are ensured by the organization in which a well-built and effective corporate culture operates.

THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF RESEARCH.

At present, interest in such a phenomenon as corporate culture has unusually increased. Moreover, this interest is growing, both from the point of view of science and theoretical aspects of this phenomenon, and from the standpoint of practical application. Such increased attention to the essence of corporate culture is

not accidental. In their work in Search of Excellence, Tom Peters and Robert Waterman say that for a long time until today, scientists and researchers have confirmed and proved the fact that the culture of any organization, firm, enterprise, etc. determines its effectiveness. It is also important to note the already proven fact that the productivity and productivity level of even the most talented and capable employees is reduced by at least two times from their potential, in the event that they find themselves in companies with a weak corporate culture[1]. Not a single enterprise, firm, organization, etc. will achieve the desired result if employees are not "charged" for success[2]. And since at present a significant number of organizations, including legendary ones, have problems with the creation, implementation and strengthening of corporate culture, and there is such a genuine interest in this phenomenon that is growing every day. The heads of such companies, having an insufficient level of knowledge regarding the essence of the concept of "corporate culture", usually rely on intuition or borrow experience already available from other companies. However, when trying to adapt someone else's model of corporate culture to your own organization, in most cases it turns out that such a method is not only absolutely ineffective, but also destructive in some cases. Copying a foreign culture does not have a sufficient level of motivation, and therefore is not suitable and does not carry practical benefits.

Why is corporate culture so important? The modern world is inevitably changing, leaving behind the in-

dustrial society, and using all the experience accumulated by mankind, we are moving to a post-industrial society. In such a world, the dominant and most important production resource is information. As Professor Daniel Bell of Harvard University notes, the post-industrial society is characterized, first of all, by the dominance of scientific developments over any other human activity. The knowledge industry will become the primary driving force of the economy[3]. From all of the above, it follows that the main treasure of the post-industrial society is a person as a carrier of information. A highly educated person, a professional with knowledge and information. In other words, human

capital is the main condition for development. It can be said with confidence that all existing organizations striving to achieve success are faced with the need to rally employees at all stages of production. Thus, a certain social organism is formed, living according to the same rules, striving for the same goal, having a similar system of motivation. Let's assume that this "social organism" is a firm, company, organization, etc., then the condition for its successful functioning will be a favorable environment. This environment is an effective corporate culture.

Edgar Schein identifies three levels of corporate culture, which are presented in picture 1.

Surface level	Subsurface level	Deep level
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • External factors: • patterns of behavior; • communication style; • technologies; • architecture; • style of clothes; • emotional atmosphere; • workplace; • symbols, rituals and ceremonies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Value orientations and beliefs: • common beliefs; • moral views; • ethical rules; • strategy; • philosophy; • values; • Code of Conduct; • goals and goals. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic suggestions: • the meaning of objects and phenomena; • understanding of time and space; • attitude towards a person and his activity; • beliefs and attitudes.

Picture 1. Levels of corporate culture according to E. Schein[4].

Frank Harris and Richard Moran form six basic building blocks of corporate culture elements:[5]

1. Philosophy of the company. Includes:
 - Mission.
 - Values.
 - Principles of work of firm.
2. Value-normative culture. Includes:
 - Ethical codes.
 - Company standards.
3. Culture of internal communications. Includes:
 - Meetings and meetings.
 - Information stands.
 - Corporate publications.
4. Socio-psychological culture. Includes:
 - Socio-psychological climate.
 - System of stimulation and motivation of work.
5. Event culture. Includes:
 - Corporate myths, legends, stories.
 - Ceremonies and holidays.
 - Traditions.
6. Culture of external identification. Includes:
 - Corporate color.
 - Trademark.
 - Tagline.
 - Logo.

According to Kodzhaspirova Galina Mikhailovna, Doctor of Philosophy, institutions of additional education are educational institutions that implement additional educational programs of various directions that go beyond the main educational programs in order to fully meet the needs of citizens, society, and the state[6]. These include advanced training institutions, courses, vocational guidance centers, music and art schools, art schools, children's art houses, stations for

young technicians, stations for young naturalists, etc. According to Krylov A. N. Corporate culture is a set of ideas, values, generally recognized models and norms of behavior inherent in a particular organization, the joint experience of members of the organization, formed in the course of collective activity and expressed in both material and spiritual forms.

FOREIGN ASPECTS OF RESEARCH.

The diversity of views on organizational culture can be narrowed if the basis of its understanding is not attributive characteristics, the diversity of which is clearly visible in the above definitions, but a system of general methodological principles underlying them. Both foreign and domestic specialists refer to the corporate principles as follows: continuous development and improvement (the implementation of this principle consists in an adequate assessment of oneself, determining one's strengths and weaknesses, the desire to improve both individual and collective knowledge and skills); optimism (people in the company are convinced that they carry a powerful positive charge, which is reflected in relations between employees, with customers, suppliers and even competitors); mutual support (the ability to work in a team acts as a value); professionalism and competence (everyone does what he can do better than others, sharing his experience and findings)[7]. A number of specialists, noting the importance of the position of managers of different levels to the formation of a corporate culture, highlight the principles of management (effective joint work of the manager and employees; joint development of goals and their achievement; monitoring and checking progress in achieving goals; advising and supporting employees in the performance of tasks; employees of the organization's values; creating favorable working conditions so that the work and efforts of employees give

the greatest effect) and interactions (constant and systematic exchange of information; accessibility of management to employees of the organization; politeness and correctness of employees in relation to each other).

In general, the concepts of organizational (corporate) culture, with a certain degree of conventionality, can be divided into two main groups: rational-pragmatic, considering corporate culture as an attribute of the organization and suggesting the ability to influence its formation, and phenomenological, interpreting culture as the purpose of the very essence of the organization and denying the possibility of purposeful direct influence on its formation. The first approach gives access to technological opportunities in the management of organizational culture, and the second one shows the uniqueness of the formation of corporate culture, the synergy of its existence. The combination of these two trends provides the creation of the optimal direction in the formation and development of the culture of the organization and increase its efficiency [8,9].

ANALYSIS AND RESULT.

Modern managers are aware of the importance of corporate culture for the development of an organization: it gives employees an organizational identity, defines an intra-group view of the company, being an important source of stability and continuity in the organization, which creates a sense of reliability of the organization itself and their position in it, contributes to the formation of a sense of social security; knowledge of the basics of the organizational culture of your company helps new employees to correctly interpret the events taking place in the organization, identifying all the most important and essential in them; Intra-organizational culture, more than anything else, stimulates the self-awareness and high responsibility of the employee who performs the tasks assigned to him.

An empirical analysis of the management activities of a number of successful enterprises suggests that attention to corporate culture becomes scientifically necessary in the presence of the following factors: the existing corporate culture does not correspond to the strategic goals of the organization; any innovations are met with active resistance from employees, which does not allow supporting dynamic development and innovation[2][8]; they are so satisfied with the working conditions that they lose the initiative, cease to be active; the existing corporate culture does not act as a factor in motivating employees for high achievements.

The formed corporate culture speaks of the complete identification of the employee with the company and means that he not only realizes the ideals of the company, clearly observes the rules and norms of behavior in the organization, but also internally fully accepts corporate values. In this case, the cultural values of the organization become the individual values of the employee, occupying a strong place in the motivational structure of his behavior[9]. The development of a corporate culture in the direction of increasing the innovative susceptibility and activity of the personnel makes it possible to ensure that the strategic objectives of the company and the trends of innovative development in the industry and the community as a whole are in line and balanced, to increase the creative activity of em-

ployees, stimulating the growth of proposals for improving processes and other organizational changes related to increasing efficiency and management effectiveness, accelerate the process of integration and the formation of effective teams in the company that implement innovative projects. The carriers of the innovative corporate culture are the head of the organization and top managers, who will "broadcast" elements of the culture to subordinates [10]. In the last decade, a new strategic approach to the development of an organization has been formed - a customer-oriented approach that ensures an increase in its competitiveness and growth in profitability by mobilizing all its resources to identify, engage, attract customers and retain the most profitable of them by improving the quality of service and satisfying customer needs. It replaces the still prevailing product-oriented approach.

CONCLUSION.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the basis for efficient operation and investment attractiveness of a joint-stock company is the environment of social cooperation and mutual trust between all members of the corporate community. For its formation, it is necessary to adhere to the principles of corporate behavior, and its content is aimed at building trust in the emerging relations related to the management of a joint-stock company. In the context of the globalization of the world economy, it is necessary to create the basic principles for the effective formation of the corporate culture of joint-stock companies.

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